

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Implementation of content marketing strategies in micro and small enterprises in Makassar City - Indonesia

Muhammad Nureski Muis, Muhammad Rakib * and Muhammad Jamil

Department of Business and Entrepreneurship, Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Makassar, Indonesia.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 25(01), 1415-1422

Publication history: Received on 25 November 2024; revised on 13 January 2025; accepted on 19 January 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.25.1.0024>

Abstract

The implementation of the content marketing strategy at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” in building customer engagement. This research used a qualitative method with data collection techniques through observation and the distribution of questionnaires to the followers of the SMEs Instagram account. The results of the study indicate that the implementation of the content marketing strategy through content idea development, copywriting, editing, and the use of relevant captions and hashtags successfully increased customer interaction on social media. The number of followers and sales increased significantly after the implementation of this strategy. The study concludes that content marketing is effective in increasing customer engagement and driving sales growth at Micro and Small Enterprises.

Keywords: Content Marketing; Customer Engagement; Business; Social Media; Digital Marketing

1. Introduction

The marketing concept has undergone significant changes, from focusing on products (Marketing 1.0) to being more customer-oriented (Marketing 2.0) to being centered on human values (Marketing 3.0). Technological advances are bringing the economy towards digital, creating Marketing 4.0 [1]. Social media has now become an important part of life, beyond its function as a communication platform for building networks and influencing public opinion [1] [2] The development of internet networks throughout the country has also increased people's access to the internet [3].

The number of social media users in Indonesia which is in line with increasing internet access. Based on Central Bureau of Statistics data, the percentage of the population accessing the internet rose from 57.33% in 2017 to 82.07% in 2021. This was driven by the ease of internet access through various media, such as *wifi*, public facilities and cell phones. The increasing trend in the use of social media has also made it an effective marketing tool, because it is more measurable and has a quick impact in attracting consumer interest in products or services [4].

Content marketing is a strategy for attracting new audiences and introducing business, as well as turning audiences into loyal customers [5]. Additionally, content marketing helps companies collect valuable data that can be used to tailor content to be more relevant to audience needs, thereby increasing campaign effectiveness. Appropriate content helps build customer engagement, which functions as a long-term investment for the company through customer

engagement value. Thus, customer engagement not only strengthens the relationship with the audience, but also strengthens the company's overall content marketing strategy.

In this context, content marketing is a strategy designed to attract the attention of a new audience with the goal of introducing an established business. Once the audience becomes familiar with the business, content marketing aims to

* Corresponding author: Muhammad Rakib.

encourage them to transition into customers and to ensure that those who have already made purchases remain loyal to the company's products [6].

Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah" is an SMEs that focuses on coffee products and faces the challenge of differentiating itself from competitors. Through content marketing strategies, they strive to introduce products, educate customers about coffee, and build emotional connections with their audience to increase customer engagement. The Instagram account @sentrakopitoraja has 140 followers with 29 posts, but activity is still minimal. Therefore, the content marketing strategy implementation plan aims to increase customer engagement and expand brand recognition in the digital world. This research focuses on how Content Marketing strategies can build brand awareness, increase Customer Engagement, and encourage conversions, with the hope of creating informative, relevant content, and building customer loyalty.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Digital Marketing

Digital Marketing is an application of the internet and is related to digital technology which is connected to traditional communication to achieve marketing goals [7]. Some examples of online platforms that are used by marketers to promote their products and interact with potential consumers include websites, blogs and social media (such as Instagram, WhatsApp, Line and others) [8].

2.2. Content Marketing

One of the important aspects of content marketing is the ability to attract attention with relevant, informative and interesting content, so that brands can win the attention of their audience [9]. A content marketing strategy should be based on a deep understanding of the needs of the target audience. In addition, content marketing also aims to build trust by providing accurate and transparent information, which can strengthen customer relationships and loyalty [10]. Thus, the media obtained by the company is the exposure gained through word of mouth. If the company's quality is very high, people will usually make it go viral through social media and communities. Media exposure can also result from strong public relations and media efforts, creating what is known as word of mouth [11]. The Content Marketing indicators according to include: (1) Reader Cognition: The audience's ability to understand content in various forms (visual, audio, kinaesthetic interaction), (2) Sharing Motivation: The audience's motivation to share content to enhance self-image and expand their network, (3) Persuasion: The company's ability to attract the audience to try their products or services, and (4) Decision Making: The influence of content on audience decisions, supported by trust, facts, emotions, and efficiency [12].

2.3. Planning Strategy for Compiling Content Marketing

Basically, Content Marketing involves the process of creating and distributing content. Effective implementation of Content Marketing requires marketers to produce original content within the company, or utilize external company sources. Marketers must also understand the distribution channels that will be used to distribute the content.

Based on the view, the following are the main steps in Content Marketing planning [11]. Here is a summary of the sentences you provided are: (1) Setting Goals: It is important for marketers to determine clear goals before content production, according to business targets and have evaluation indicators. The main goal of Content Marketing is to increase sales and strengthen the brand, including awareness, association, and brand loyalty, (2) Audience Mapping: After setting goals, marketers must define the target audience specifically to create more relevant content, (3) Content Planning and Ideation: Composing content ideas and planning with the right themes, formats, and narratives for the success of the campaign, (4) Content Production. Content production requires dedication of time and cost, as well as full commitment from marketers, (5) Content Distribution: Marketers need an effective distribution strategy so that content can reach audiences through owned, paid, and earned media, and (6) Content Marketing Development: Content Marketing allows monitoring performance based on themes, formats, and distribution channels. Marketers need to develop content regularly and choose the right types of content, such as videos, images, and infographics [13].

2.4. Customer Engagement

Customer Engagement is the process of developing a customer portfolio consisting of high-value customer groups and maintaining ongoing relationships with them [14]. Customer Engagement occurs when internet users interact or collaborate with brands, companies, or fellow users. This involves an emotional and intellectual connection with the

user. Marketers engage users by persuading them to participate in the content or media provided, both online and offline.

Customer Engagement is a strategic effort to create, build, and strengthen relationships with customers, which is key to maintaining future business performance [15]. Customer Engagement is a development of relationship marketing, because relationship marketing focuses more on exchange transactions between consumers and service providers. In contrast, customer engagement focuses more on consumer experience, thus creating an emotional connection [16]. There are three main indicators of customer engagement: (1) Multimedia Content: Engaging content that appeals to users' senses, such as status updates, photos, videos, and links, (2) Product Description: Detailed information about the product, including its description, and (3) Entertainment: Entertaining content, such as memes, that attracts audiences to the company's website or social media [17].

3. Methodology

In this research, the type of research used is qualitative, where this research aims to understand the phenomena experienced by research subjects, such as behavior, perceptions, motivations and actions, as a whole. This research was carried out in August 2024. This research was carried out at cf. This research focuses on activities in preparing the Content Marketing strategy implemented by the Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah" as well as the forms of Customer Engagement from these SMEs. The data source used in this research is primary data obtained directly from the first source through questionnaires and observation instruments. Descriptive analysis technique is a method used to analyze data by describing or describing the data that has been collected. This method aims to present clear and structured information regarding the characteristics of a phenomenon or event being studied.

4. Results And Discussion

4.1. Implementation of Content Marketing Strategy

The implementation results of the strategies that have been implemented can be seen as follows:

4.1.1. Content ideas

The initial stage of creating content marketing is to develop content ideas that are relevant and interesting, tailored to business goals, characteristics of the target market, and the uniqueness of the Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah" product. The main focus is customer education about types of coffee and their health benefits. These ideas are packaged in formats such as single images, carousels and videos to build customer engagement. The implementation is shown in the image below.

Figure 1 Application of content marketing to the Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah"

Figure 1 shows several types of digital marketing content for coffee products, such as Reels, Carousel, and Single Image. Reels consist of short videos that highlight users' reactions after trying coffee, utilizing elements of humour to attract

viewers' attention. This strategy is designed to make the product easier to remember and give a pleasant impression, thereby increasing interaction with the audience.

4.1.2. Copywriting

At this stage, copywriting aims to produce interesting and effective text that is in line with the "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah" brand identity. Each word is carefully chosen to highlight the uniqueness of the product, attract the audience, and increase customer engagement through social media and product descriptions in simple and relevant language. An example of its application is as shown in this image

Figure 2 Application of Copywriting

The image above introduces the product "Bland Ground Coffee" from a mixture of Arabica (70%) and Robusta (30%) coffee beans from Tana Toraja. Product descriptions highlight aspects of locality and authenticity of ingredients to create an emotional bond with consumers. The use of simple language makes it easier for the audience to understand the quality of the product and encourages them to try and share their experiences on social media. This copywriting approach not only offers quality coffee, but also presents stories that are relevant to audience Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah".

4.1.3. Editing

At this stage, the content that has been created, such as text, images and videos, will go through an editing process to ensure that it appears attractive, informative, relevant and in accordance with the values of Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah". This process includes checking language style, sentence structure, and appropriateness of communication tone, as well as aligning image and video quality. Edited content is ready to publish to attract attention and increase customer engagement.

4.1.4. Caption & Hashtags

Captions are an important element in the content marketing strategy at Business "Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah", designed personally and communicatively to build relationships with the audience. Each caption reflects the uniqueness of the coffee product, educates the audience, and invites interaction through invitations or questions. An example of its use is as shown in the image below

Figure 3 Application of Captions & Hashtags

In the picture above, the use of simple and effective language is prioritized so that the message is easy to understand. In addition, the selection of relevant hashtags, such as #kopiToraja, #CitaRasaNusantara and #kopi1000Nurhidayah, aims to expand reach and attract audiences interested in local products, increasing content engagement on social media.

4.1.5. Publish

After the content has been created, the next step is to publish it on social media at the right time and frequency, and use interesting captions and hashtags. Performance is monitored to measure results such as likes, shares and comments, to increase customer engagement and improve content strategy.

4.2. Impact of implementing content marketing

The implementation of the content marketing strategy at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” has had a significant positive impact, especially in increasing brand awareness, expanding the audience, and encouraging increased sales.

4.2.1. Increasing the number of followers and interactions on Instagram

As a result of implementing a consistent content marketing strategy, the Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah”. Instagram account showed a significant increase in the number of followers. This is also accompanied by increased interaction from the audience, which includes likes, comments and sharing content. The following graph shows the trend of increasing the number of followers along with increasingly active engagement on Instagram.

Figure 4 Increase in the Number of Followers

One of the impacts of implementing content marketing at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” is the increase in the number of Instagram followers, from initially 140 to 683. This growth occurred because the content presented was not only informative but also entertaining and appropriate to the target audience. Posts in the form of product photos, quotes, quizzes and memes have succeeded in attracting the interest of new users.

Figure 5 Number of Interactions

Implementing a content marketing strategy at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” has been proven to increase interaction and engagement on social media, especially on Instagram. The number of followers increased from 140 to 636, with various interesting content, such as quotes, quizzes, memes and product information.

- **Content Type:** Content is published in single picture, carousel and reels formats according to the topic. Wednesday's memes generated 146 engagements, and "To Jolo" reels reached 117, demonstrating the effectiveness of content variety.
- **Engagement:** Informative content such as quotes and quizzes get the highest response. For example, quotes on Monday achieved 162 likes and total engagement of 168, while quizzes on Tuesday received 121 likes and engagement of 126.
- **Time and Frequency of Publication:** Consistently posting content every Monday to Friday at 10:00-11:00 is successful in maintaining audience interest and engagement.

Overall, this data shows that the content marketing strategy implemented by Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” is very effective in building customer engagement. With a variety of content, consistent publications and relevant topics, this MSME is able to significantly increase reach and interaction with the audience on social media platforms.

4.2.2. Increased number of sales

An effective content marketing strategy at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” has succeeded in increasing engagement and sales. Content that highlights unique Flavors and testimonials on social media strengthens the trust of potential buyers, encouraging more people to try the product. The increase in monthly sales can be seen in the following graph.

Figure 6 Total of Sales at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah”

In the period April to July, *Sentra Kopi Toraja* has not implemented a content marketing strategy, but sales still show a stable trend even without a significant increase. In August, after implementing the content marketing strategy, sales increased sharply to IDR 8,320,000, showing the positive impact of content marketing in attracting consumers and increasing their engagement. This strategy has proven effective in driving sales and has the potential to become a sustainable move.

The implementation of content marketing strategy in building customer engagement in Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” has a positive impact on this strategy which attracts attention and increases customer interaction, in line with Kotler & Keller's (2016) view on the importance of engagement in digital marketing. In the early stages, Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” focused on developing content ideas that were not only informative, but also relevant to the audience.

5. Conclusion

The implementation of Content Marketing strategies at Business “Kopi 1000 Nurhidayah” has proven to be effective in building customer engagement. This is demonstrated by increased interaction on social media, both in the form of likes, comments and shares, as well as an increase in the number of followers on Instagram accounts. Apart from that, this strategy has also succeeded in strengthening the relationship between brands and consumers, which can be seen from increased brand loyalty and awareness. This positive impact is also reflected in increased product sales, which shows that the Content Marketing strategy is not only able to attract consumers' attention but also encourage them to make purchases.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] M. Rakib, F. Azis, D. A. Sanusi, A. Ab, and M. Taufik, 2024. How Does Government Support, Finance, Family Environment and Information Technology Influence Sustainable Entrepreneurship?, *Journal of Law and Sustainable Development*, 12(1), p. 1–21, 2024, [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.55908/sdgs.v12i1.2499>
- [2] D. Teselios and M. Savu, 2018. Social Media-An Integral Part of Daily Life, *J. Contemp. Econ. (Revista Econ. Contemmporana)*, 3(1), p. 59–78.
- [3] S. Rohadian and M. T. Amir, 2019. Upaya Membangun Customer Engagement Melalui Media Sosial Instagram, *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Management and Industry (JEMI)*, 2(4), doi: 10.36782/jemi.v2i4.1925.
- [4] K. Jamil, L. Dunnan, R. F. Gul, M. U. Shehzad, S. H. M. Gillani, and F. H. Awan, 2022. Role of Social Media Marketing Activities in Influencing Customer Intentions: A Perspective of a New Emerging Era, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.808525.

- [5] M. Najib, M. Dimas, J. Diningrat, and M. Rakib, 2024. Marketing Strategy for Digital-Based Bread Products to Increase Sales (Case Study of the Gembong Ratu Bread Business, Gowa Regency, South Sulawesi Province), *Quest Journals Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 12(1), p. 69–77.
- [6] A. A. Azzahrah, M. Rakib, and M. Jufri, 2023. Product Diversification to Increase Consumer Satisfaction: A Development Research Study, *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 6(11), p. 7291–7296, 2023, doi: 10.47191/ijcsrr/v6-i11-33.
- [7] D. Ryan and C. Jones, 2019. *Understanding Digital Marketing Marketing strategies for engaging the digital generation*, London Philadelphia New Delhi. KoganPage.
- [8] D. A. Sanusi, A. Widodo, and L. Tunjanan, 2023. Media Literacy, Consumer Trust, Product Prices, Distribution, and Purchasing Decisions in Online Business: A Study of Students at Satya Wiyata Mandala University, Indonesian of *Journal Business and Entrepreneurship Research.*, 1(1), p. 52–61, [Online]. Available: <https://journal.unm.ac.id/index.php/IJOB/article/view/119%0Ahttps://journal.unm.ac.id/index.php/IJOB/ER/article/download/119/110>
- [9] K. K. Kapoor, K. Tamilmani, N. P. Rana, P. Patil, Y. K. Dwivedi, and S. Nerur, 2018. *Advances in Social Media Research*, *Information Systems Frontiers*, 20(3), p. 531–558.
- [10] M. Akbar, M. Rakib, A. Isma, and D. A. Sanusi, 2024. Development of Sustainable Business Models through Internal Partnerships Efforts to Expand Consumer Reach, *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 7(3), p. 1904–1909, 2024, doi: 10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i3-52.
- [11] P. Kotler, H. Kartajaya, and I. Setiawan, 2017. *Marketing 4.0(Moving From Traditional To Digital)* Philip Kotler. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Hoboken, New Jersey
- [12] E. Septiarini and Ezra Karamang, 2023. Pengaruh Instagram Konten Marketing terhadap Purchase Intention Membership Fitness Center yang Dimediasi Brand Engagement,” *Journal of Trends Economics and Accounting Research.*, 4(2), p. 338–345, doi: 10.47065/jtear.v4i2.1007.
- [13] M. Stokes, P. Baeck, and T. Baker, May 2017. *What Next For Digital Social Innovation? Realising The Potential Of People And Technology To Tackle Social Challenges.*
- [14] K. R. Alok and M. Srivastava, 2013. The Antecedents of Customer Loyalty: An Empirical Investigation in Life Insurance Context, *Journal of Competitiveness.*, 5(2), p. 139–163, doi: 10.7441/joc.2013.02.10.
- [15] R. J. Brodie, L. D. Hollebeek, B. Jurić, and A. Ilić, 2011. Customer engagement: Conceptual domain, fundamental propositions, and implications for research, *Journal of Service Research.*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 252–271, doi: 10.1177/1094670511411703.
- [16] V. Riorini and C. C. Widayati, 2015. Relationship Commitment and Customer Engagement, *Jurnal MIX*, 5(3), p. 418–436.
- [17] F. S. Farook and N. Abeysekara, 2016. Influence of Social Media Marketing on Customer Engagement, *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 5(12), p. 115–125.